

SCHOOL HISTORY EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN IN 1918-1940: HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE PROBLEM.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17106788>

Annotation

As a result of the Bolsheviks' rise to power, large-scale reforms began not only in the political, but also in the social sphere. The development of public education in the Turkestan ASSR and the Uzbek SSR in 1918-1940, the organization of new Soviet schools and the establishment of the educational process, and the provision of schools with teaching staff and educational and methodological literature were studied from the first years of Soviet power until its collapse. During the Soviet era, a totalitarian regime was established, ideological pluralism was suppressed, and a Marxist-Leninist worldview was established in the cultural and spiritual life of society. This circumstance inevitably influenced the development of science, in particular historical science. Evaluating past events based on a class-based approach, condemning the past, and idealizing the socialist system became commonplace.

Key words: Turkestan ASSR (Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic), TASSR CEC (Central Executive Committee), People's Commissariat of Education, military communism, unified labor school, Labor school – communes

1. Introduction

It is necessary to comprehensively analyze the processes of formation and development of the public education system in our republic in the 20-30s, which are full of contradictions in historical science today, and the reforms in the national education system during that complex period.

Research on the development of the education system in the Turkestan ASSR and the Uzbek SSR in 1918-1940 and the establishment of the teaching of history in Soviet schools in this process can be divided into the following 3 groups according to periodic, geographical, and ideological aspects within the framework of the topic:

- 1) literature created during the Soviet period;
- 2) works of foreign authors;
- 3) research conducted in Uzbekistan during the years of independence.

2. Methods and degree of study:

The article is based on generally accepted historical methods - historicity, comparative-logical analysis, consistency, and objectivity principles, and shows that art forms the spiritual basis of society's development from a historical perspective.

3. Results of the discussion:

The development of public education in the Turkestan ASSR and the Uzbek SSR in 1918-1940, the organization of new Soviet schools and the establishment of the educational process, and the provision of schools with teaching staff and educational and methodological literature were studied from the first years of Soviet power until its collapse. During the Soviet era, a totalitarian regime was established, ideological pluralism was suppressed, and a Marxist-Leninist worldview was established in the cultural and spiritual life of society. This circumstance inevitably influenced the development of science, in particular historical science. Evaluating past events based on a class-based approach, condemning the past, and idealizing the socialist system became commonplace. That is why the works created during this period are similar to each other in their ideological content. However, the research published in the early 20s and later 1985-1990s differs somewhat from the literature published in the 30s and 70s.

The first work published in the 1920s, directly related to the issue of teaching school history, was created by N.P. Arkhangelsky. Since he was an employee of the People's Commissariat of Education of the TASSR, he reflected on the state of teaching history in schools of the region and existing problems. The author, supporting active learning methods and critical thinking, emphasized the need to use new methods in teaching history. In addition, he called for the use of local languages in teaching in the schools of Central Asia.

Also, relatively accurate information about the national education system and Soviet schools in the Turkestan ASSR can be found in the works of P.I. Serbov and A.D. Nikiforov. The authors expressed their relatively critical opinion that in the first years after the revolution, the Soviets opened countless schools in Turkestan, without taking into account the existing conditions, the issue of personnel, and the material situation, as a result of which the sphere of education reached a very deplorable state.

Starting in the 1930s, the ideological situation in the country changed dramatically, and historical science began to become increasingly politicized. A class-based, party-based approach to assessing social processes has been definitively established. Historians began to evaluate the activities of the Soviet

state, including its policy in the field of education, only positively. During this period, publications devoted to the history of culture and education were mainly generalizing, containing only positive information about the development of education.

In particular, the collection published by the People's Commissariat of Education on the occasion of the 15th anniversary of the Uzbek SSR contains articles and memoirs of scientists and workers in the field, which discuss the achievements of the republic in the field of education and cultural-educational work. Although this collection is written in a solemn spirit characteristic of anniversary publications, it contains several noteworthy factual information related to the development of education. At the same time, the articles included in the collection contain many conclusions and judgments of a propaganda nature, not based on evidence. For example, in A.N. Ovsyannikov's article, an attempt was made to link some shortcomings and deficiencies in public education with the machinations of "bourgeois nationalists" and "counter-revolutionary elements."

In the article of V.M. Dmitriev, included in this collection, the author gives a brief overview of the history of the education system in Turkestan and highlights the issue of the organization of the education system in the Uzbek SSR and the training of personnel. The article was written in the spirit of repressive policy, stating that Inogamov and his supporters worked as "enemies of the people" in the apparatus of the People's Commissariat of Education.

The article by P.Y. Serbov reflects the work carried out on the training of subject teachers, including history teachers, in full-time and correspondence departments of higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan. The 40s-50s were also not an easy period in terms of the development of historiography. During this period, the study of existing negative phenomena in society was prohibited, and scholars were required to show the "advantages" of Soviet society. Therefore, in the 40s, works on the history of the education system were interpreted only in a positive spirit, in which the achievements in this area were mainly interpreted as the result of "the instructions of the leaders Lenin and Stalin and the wise leadership of the Communist Party.

In the 40s, when the education system in Soviet-style schools was established to a certain extent, attention began to be paid to extracurricular activities to improve the quality of education. For example, the proposals of N.P. Arkhangelsky in his treatise on the organization of excursions and trips in order to develop local history skills in school education are noteworthy. However, the

brochure pays special attention to excursions related to such subjects as geography and biology, and there is almost no information about the organization of excursions and trips of students to historical museums, historical places and cities.

In the 50s of the 20th century, special attention began to be paid to the development of the science of history teaching methodology. One of the first works devoted to this issue is a textbook by N.V. Andreevskaya and V.N. Bernadsky. The authors consider various aspects of the methodology of teaching history, the development of Russian scientific-methodological thinking in the context of historical science before the revolution and during the years of Soviet power, the introduction of "struggle for modernity" in school history education in the first years after the revolution and the introduction of "sociology" (sociology) instead of history; the prevalence of vulgar-materialistic and sociological approaches in the study of history and sociology; Due to "methodical" fanaticism, such issues as the establishment of ineffective work methods in school practice, such as the "laboratory-team method," "workbooks," "journal-textbooks," are highlighted.

As a shortcoming of this work, it can be noted that, based on the socio-political environment of that time, the authors overestimated the role of I.V. Stalin in the development of the system of teaching history in schools.

The organization of the Soviet-type education system is highlighted in the work of T.N. Qori-Niyozov. However, since the organization of new types of schools in this work is mainly covered in a Soviet spirit, it is necessary to critically evaluate the work.

Among the studies published in the 1950s, S. Rajabov's monograph stands out. The monograph provides a retrospective overview of the development of education in Central Asia before the revolution, with the main focus on the development of school education before and during the Second World War - based on official documents, archival data, and press materials. The author provides information about the experience of advanced teachers and provides a lot of interesting information about the teaching of history and "Fundamentals of the Constitution" in the schools of the republic in 1935-1940. However, the author does not indicate the source of some of the cited factual materials. At the same time, the work was created on the basis of a class approach and a one-sided approach to reality.

I. Kadyrov's treatise also discusses the "pathetic" state of public education in the pre-revolutionary period and the "great" achievements made during the

years of Soviet power. The work is written in the spirit of glorifying the Soviet government, and the author cites many facts and figures related to the development of public education in the years following the October Revolution, but does not pay attention to the fact that quantitative changes in the field of education of that period were not always accompanied by qualitative changes.

By the 50s and 60s, archival and legislative documents, as well as memoir sources, began to be used in research on the development of education. An example of this is the work of K.E. Bendrikov. The author illuminates the development of public education in the first years of Soviet power, using legislative acts, archival data, memoir sources, and available literature. However, the author did not widely use press materials, which are considered one of the important sources, and did not systematically analyze statistical data. Also, the fact that it was intended to show the Soviet school as the most exemplary school indicates that the work was written on the basis of communist ideology.

In the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, a number of new works reflecting the history of public education were published. In particular, it is worth noting the third volume of the four-volume fundamental work dedicated to the history of Uzbekistan. Although this work is also written in the spirit of communist ideology, the information contained in it provides an opportunity to form a general idea of the state and development trends of education in the 20s and 30s.

In the 1970s, a number of studies were conducted on the general trends in the development of school education. They spoke about the ideological views that during the Soviet period, the Uzbek script was first transitioned to Latin, and later to Russian graphics, as well as that the establishment of the Soviet regime led to the development of the Uzbek people in all spheres under the "wise leadership of the communist party."

4. Conclusions

Thus, the description of the literature devoted to the topic indicates that in historical literature, the development of public education in Uzbekistan in 1917-1940 was studied quite thoroughly. In particular, such issues as the process of organizing Soviet schools, strengthening their material and technical base, training pedagogical personnel, and providing students with textbooks, study guides, and other educational equipment are widely covered. However, no fundamental research has been conducted on the issue of teaching history in schools established in the first decades of Soviet power.

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